

Annex to: Update of the risk assessment of mineral oil hydrocarbons in food.
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Annex B - Analytical methods for the quantification and characterisation of mineral oil hydrocarbons in food

B.2. Sample preparation methods

Sample preparation needs to be adjusted to the type of sample. Some critical points are: the extraction solvent needs to be adequate for the pre-separation by HPLC, i.e. end up with hexane. Extraction of solids (foods or packaging materials) may be hindered by slow diffusion within the sample. As in the case of recycled cardboard, the solvent also has to swell the matrix, e.g. using ethanol that can later be removed from hexane by addition of water. Furthermore, extraction has to discriminate against the high molecular mass hydrocarbons, such as hot melts and polyolefin oligomers, as these may disturb (overload) GC analysis (Lorenzini et al., 2010). For wet solid samples, water may form a barrier against extraction with hexane; first the water needs to be largely replaced by ethanol before extraction with hexane becomes possible.

The extraction yield cannot be tested by standard addition, since the added standards will remain on the surface of the samples. Completeness must be checked by re-extraction under accentuated conditions, such as substantially longer times and increased temperature.

Mostly natural n-alkanes can be excluded during integration, but in some foods they are present in such large quantities that they disturb the MOSH analysis and must be removed by means of activated aluminium oxide processing (Fiselier et al., 2009a, b). However, since aluminium oxide treatment may also eliminate some MOSH other than n-alkanes, it should only be applied when necessary.

Olefins (e.g. squalene, sterenes, carotenoids), contained in many foods, particularly vegetable oils, are not separated from the MOH (mainly MOAH) by the HPLC used. Again, they may be excluded during integration, but the amounts may be so high that they hide the MOAH hump. Commonly their polarity is increased by means of epoxidation before the measurement, moving them behind the MOAH fraction (Nestola and Schmidt, 2017; Biedermann et al., 2020). However, since epoxidation also affects some MOAH, reducing their total concentration by 20-35 %, it should only be applied when necessary.

In some foods, such as infant milk powder, encapsulated MOH need to be made accessible, e.g. by reconstitution and saponification.

B.2. Challenges by the food matrix

With a simple matrix, such as rice from a jute bag that has been treated with batching oil, a complex sample preparation is unnecessary. Direct extraction from the surface of the rice grains with hexane results in a complete yield (see Figure B1 for MOAH).

Figure B1. Basmati rice; HPLC-GC-FID chromatogram from a MOAH hump with the internal standards pentylbenzene (5B), 2-methylnaphthalene (2-MN), 1-methylnaphthalene (1-MN), 1,3,5-tri-tertbutylbenzene (TBB) and perylene (Per) after direct extraction with hexane.

In other foods, ingredients can mimic MOAH. These do not result in a hump, but are present as riding peaks or clusters of peaks that may hide the MOSH or MOAH hump. In Figure B2, the first cluster is from squalene, its isomerization products and steranes, the second from isomerized carotenoids.

Figure B2. HPLC-GC-FID chromatogram from a MOAH fraction obtained from a nougat spread with cocoa and vegetable oils (rapeseed and palm oil) as an ingredient without epoxidation. The MOAH-hump is hidden by the clusters of peaks.

These substances can be removed by epoxidation, allowing the MOAH hump to become clearly visible (Figure B3)

Figure B3. HPLC-GC-FID chromatogram from a MOAH fraction obtained from the nougat spread with cocoa and vegetable oils after epoxidation; now a clear hump of MOAH is visible.

B.3. Compositional analysis of MOSH and MOAH by GCxGC

HPLC-GC-FID is currently state of the art for MOSH and MOAH analysis. Almost all monitoring data were determined using this technique, and the exposure assessment in the opinion is largely based on it. GCxGC is the method of choice for a more detailed analysis. It is more complex than HPLC-GC-FID and currently only used by a minority of the laboratories. It is particularly useful for clarifying results obtained by HPLC-GC, which, however, is only needed for a small proportion of all samples.

Figure B4 shows the power of GCxGC by comparing conventional monodimensional GC-FID chromatograms with plots obtained by GCxGC-FID for a paraffin oil (a white mineral oil; left) and the MOSH isolated from human fat tissue (right; Biedermann et al., 2015). For the sake of comparison, the same chromatographic system was used, but for monodimensional GC the modulator was not activated. In monodimensional GC, most of the material is represented by the hump of unresolved hydrocarbons. For GCxGC, the modulator was activated, stopping the material eluted from the first-dimension column during 6 s. For the plots shown at the bottom, the roughly 300 second dimension chromatograms obtained in a run were turned by 90° to form a quasi-three-dimensional landscape, showing a broad "hill" topped by sharp peaks. This presentation is useful on a computer screen that allows inspection from various angles and well shows the hump of the still

unresolved material, but for printing, the view from the top is clearer (center). Now the separation in the horizontal axis is the same as in the above conventional chromatograms. The vertical axis presents the retention in the second dimension, with a maximum retention time corresponding to the cycle time (6 s in this case). Components form peaks standing vertical to the plane, here with their size/height being displayed by their darkness. The hump is shown as grey field, again with the height depicted by darkness.

With GCxGC in this configuration, non-polar components are eluted early from the polar first dimension column, i.e. they enter the non-polar second column at a relatively low temperature. This accentuates the high retention power of the second dimension non-polar column for non-polar compounds and means that these are placed in the upper part of the plot. Conversely polar substances are eluted rather late, i.e. at high temperature from the first column, and pass through the second column with weak retention; they end up situated low in the plot.

Figure B4. Comparison of monodimensional GC-FID (top chromatograms) and GCxGC-FID (center and bottom) for a white mineral oil (left) and the hydrocarbons from human adipose tissue. n-Alkanes specified by carbon number; Cho, cholestane (internal standard). From Biedermann et al., 2015.

In GCxGC, two columns with different selectivity are combined, classically a non-polar first column, separating by volatility, and a polar second column. However, MOSH cannot be separated by polarity. The sometimes called 'reversed' column configuration showed better performance than the classical one. The use of a polar first dimension column (commonly with a methyl phenyl polysiloxane) combined with an apolar second dimension separation (as used in Figure B4) builds on different conformation of the molecules. Polarity by a 50 % phenyl polysiloxane provided better results than by trifluoropropyl methyl polysiloxane (Castillo et al., 2013). Other polar columns are not sufficiently thermostable.

Figure B5 compares different mineral oil products to illustrate the range of variation visible by GCxGC and provide a basis for comparison with the hydrocarbons in rat or human tissues. The oil of the upper left plot was a brownish, rather crude mineral oil fraction used for batching jute fibers. It ranged from about n-C12 to n-C33 and was dominated by the n-alkanes highlighted by a line interconnecting the center of their spots. The slanted and curved band in the upper right corner is from column bleed (visible also in other plots). Most hydrocarbons in this oil are represented by distinct signals.

The MOSH isolated from the motor oil (lower left) had been deparaffinated (removal of the n-alkanes to prevent crystallization). The n-alkanes up to n-C22 (traced by the line) are still well detectable, whereas the ones above n-C22 disappear in the iso-alkanes. In fact the dark spots on the line beyond n-C23 are iso-alkanes; the retention times of the n-alkanes 23, 25 and 30 are pointed out by dots. There are many spots above the row of n- and little branched iso-alkanes, representing multibranched paraffins. At the bottom right of this plot there are slanted rows of irregularly distributed spots that were identified by MS as steranes and hopanes. Being tetra- and pentacyclic hydrocarbons, their retention in the second dimension was low (with cholestane falling into the steranes). There is a broad cloud in the background which is due to highly isomerized components without resolution neither in the first nor the second dimension.

The MOSH of the hydraulic oil (upper right plot) was of a similarly broad range of molecular mass as the batching oil, but it was refined by deparaffination and hydrogenation, the latter forming the intense cloud mainly of naphthenes. The paraffin oil (lower right) was sold as release agent for the production of candies. It consisted of a narrow range of strongly refined distillate (n-C20 to n-C26).

Apart from the different volatility ranges, the patterns of the refined mineral oils did not fundamentally differ: the same patterns of signals were found in all samples. Some MS data are shown in Biedermann et al. (2015), pointing out that identification of a few signals enables the interpretation of a large part of GCxGC plots.

Figure B5. GCxGC plots from different mineral oil products. From Biedermann et al., 2015.

B.4. Comparison and validation of the HPLC-GC-FID results with the GCxGC

GCxGC enables differentiated analysis of MOSH and MOAH, e.g. whether the MOAH consist mainly of highly alkylated monoaromatics or 3- and multi-ring systems. Selected plots show the possibilities that GCxGC offers compared to HPLC-GC-FID.

Figure B6 shows the HPLC-GC-FID chromatogram of the MOSH fraction from a milk chocolate used for a proficiency test. The chocolate was contaminated from polypropylene, spiked with PAO (2 mg/kg), a wax (2 mg/kg) and a technical mineral oil (5 mg/kg). Apart from the internal standards (used for quantification and verification of the proper method performance), most sharp signals topping the hump are n-alkanes. Some are alternating, with predominance of the odd-numbered ones, i.e. the natural n-alkanes from cocoa. A bunch of signals at about C18 is from diterpenes in milk. A more detailed analysis was obtained by GCxGC-time of flight (TOF) mass spectrometry (Figure B7). At the top of the plot it shows highly branched oligomers from polypropylene as clusters with a difference of three carbon atoms. The presence of steranes and hopanes confirms the presence of MOSH, but the analysis reveals that the MOSH only constitute a small amount of the saturated hydrocarbons.

Figure B6. MOSH-fraction LC-GC-FID from a chocolate used in an interlaboratory test (proof-acs P2001-MRT MOSH/MOAH in chocolate by GCxGC-TOF March/April 2021).

Figure B7. MOSH-fraction GCxGC-TOF total ion chromatogram (TIC) from the chocolate of which the LC-GC-FID chromatogram was shown in Figure B6.

Figure B8 shows the HPLC-GC-FID chromatogram of the MOAH fraction of the same spiked chocolate. At best it enables to quantitate the sum of the MOAH. Using GCxGC-FID and particularly GCxGC-TOF, sensitivity is higher and it is possible to differentiate the alkylated benzenes and multi-ring aromatics by the second-dimension retention time (height in the plot; Figure B9). The bands observed in Figure B9 can be confirmed by filtering molecular masses (Figures B10 to Figure B15). Another advantage of filtering is the elimination of interfering substances. Detection using TOF is more sensitive and selective than FID, but quantification is not possible.

Figure B16 shows the PAHs (non-alkylated MOAH) in the GCxGC-TOF plot. It points out that the highly alkylated MOAH overlap with the MOAH of lower alkylation and that it is inadequate to separate MOAH by ring number using the retention times of the non-alkylated species (PAHs). If MOAH are fractionated by monodimensional GC using the PAHs, as used by Roy et al. (1985), e.g., the highly alkylated alkylbenzenes are underestimated and the MOAH with several rings overestimated, if present at all.

Figure B8. LC-GC-FID chromatogram of the MOAH-fraction of the spiked chocolate after epoxidation; the MOAH content is about 2 mg/kg.

Figure B9. GCxGC-TOF plot (TIC) of the MOAH-fraction from the chocolate after epoxidation of which the LC-GC-FID chromatogram was shown in Figure B8.

Figure B10. GCxGC-TOF TIC plot of the MOAH-fraction from the chocolate after epoxidation, using the filter for the molecular formula $C_6H_6+C(n)H(2*n)$ for all alkyl benzenes.

Figure B11. GCxGC-TOF TIC plot of the MOAH-fraction obtained from the chocolate after epoxidation, using the filter for the molecular formula $C_{10}H_8+C(n)H(2+n)$ for all alkyl naphthalenes.

Figure B12. GCxGC-TOF TIC plot of the MOAH-fraction obtained from the chocolate after epoxidation, using the filter for the molecular formula $C_{10}H_{12}+C(n)H(2*n)$ for all alkylated tetrahydro naphthalenes.

Figure B13. GCxGC-TOF TIC plot of the MOAH-fraction obtained from the chocolate after epoxidation, using the filter for the molecular formula $C_{18}H_{12}+C(n)H(2*n)$ for all alkylated benzantracenes.

Figure B14. GCxGC-TOF TIC plot of the MOAH-fraction obtained from the chocolate after epoxidation, using the filter for the molecular formula 228, 242, 256, 270, 284 (± 0.5) for chrysene (molecular mass 228) and alkylated chrysenes (with the molecular mass 242, 256, 270 and 284).

Figure B15. GCxGC-TOF TIC plot of the MOAH-fraction obtained from the chocolate after epoxidation, using the filter for the molecular formula $C_{18}H_{24}+C(n)H(2*n)$ for all alkylated dodecahydro benzantracenes.

Figure B16. GCxGC-TOF plot extracting the non-alkylated MOAH (PAH).

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